
Development of Lower Secondary School Principals in the North Central Region of Vietnam Based on A Job Position Approach: Current Situation and Solutions

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the development of lower secondary school principals based on a job-position approach in the context of comprehensive education reform in Vietnam. Grounded in both theoretical analysis and empirical investigation, the research clarifies key concepts, competency requirements, and core components of principal development, including planning, recruitment, training, evaluation, and professional working environment. A survey conducted in the North Central region of Vietnam reveals that while principals generally meet basic professional and ethical standards, limitations remain in school governance capacity, innovation, and adaptation to curriculum reform requirements. Based on these findings, the study proposes a system of solutions oriented toward competency-based planning, recruitment, professional development, performance evaluation, and enabling institutional conditions. The proposed solutions are evaluated as highly feasible and necessary by educational managers and school administrators. Overall, the study provides both theoretical and practical contributions to improving the quality of lower secondary school principals and enhancing school governance effectiveness in the context of ongoing educational reform.

KEYWORDS: Job-position approach; principal development; school leadership; school governance; competency framework; educational management; secondary education; Vietnam

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
09 April 2026

Available on:
<https://irijsh.com/>

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Vietnam's education and training system has undergone significant reforms toward modernization, international integration, and the development of high-quality human resources capable of meeting the demands of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021). In this context, educational management has shifted toward greater institutional autonomy, accountability, and school-based governance, with increasing emphasis on quality assurance and effective leadership (Dang Xuan Hai, 2019). School principals play a central role in organizing, managing, and developing educational institutions, acting as key agents in ensuring educational quality and fostering teacher professional development. Consequently, the development of a competent corps of school principals with strong leadership capacity and modern management skills has become an urgent requirement (Hoang Sy Hung, 2019; Tran Huu Hoan, 2017). To support this process, the Ministry of Education and Training has introduced professional standards for school principals, providing a framework for leadership and school governance development (MOET, 2018a). The implementation of the 2018 General Education Curriculum has further intensified these demands, particularly at the lower secondary level, which plays a crucial role in developing students' competencies and qualities (MOET, 2018b). These reforms require principals to demonstrate innovative leadership, promote teacher development, and create effective learning environments.

At the same time, public sector reforms in Vietnam have emphasized human resource management based on job positions, as reflected in regulations on job position frameworks in public service units (Government of Vietnam, 2012, 2020). This approach clarifies job functions, responsibilities, and competency requirements, providing a foundation for recruitment, training, evaluation, and personnel utilization (Bui Thi Ngoc Mai, 2018; Pham Dinh Manh, 2021). In the education sector, job position frameworks have also been introduced to standardize personnel management (MOET, 2017). Furthermore, recent policy directions, including

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the Politburo's Resolution No. 57-NQ/TW (2024) and Resolution No. 71-NQ/TW (2025), highlight the strategic importance of innovation, digital transformation, and human resource development, reinforcing the need to reform leadership development in education. The North Central region of Vietnam, comprising provinces from Thanh Hoa to Thua Thien Hue, holds strategic importance but faces challenges related to socio-economic conditions and educational quality, particularly in terms of the structure, competencies, and adaptability of lower secondary school principals.

Although there is a growing body of research on educational leadership and principal development, studies applying a job position approach remain relatively limited, especially in general education. Existing research can be categorized into several main streams, including studies on job positions in the public sector, competency frameworks based on job positions, and the application of this approach to human resource development in education. In the field of public administration, scholars have emphasized that defining job positions is essential for clarifying functions, responsibilities, and competency requirements (Trinh Xuan Thang, 2016), while job analysis has been identified as a foundational step for personnel management, including recruitment, evaluation, and training (Bui Thi Phuong Thao, 2016). Other studies have highlighted competency frameworks as key tools for effective human resource management and administrative reform (Nguyen Nhat Cuong & Nguyen Minh Ly, 2017; Pham Duc Toan & Dao Thi Thanh Thuy, 2020; Le Quan, 2016). In the field of education, research has contributed to the development of competency frameworks for educational personnel, particularly in the context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Nguyen Tien Hung, 2018). In addition, the legal and institutional framework in Vietnam, including government decrees and MOET regulations, has created favorable conditions for applying the job position approach in educational institutions (MOET, 2017, 2018a).

Some studies have begun to apply the job position approach to educational human resource development. For example, Pham Dinh Manh (2021) examined the development of university administrative staff based on job positions, highlighting the role of competency frameworks in personnel development. However, research specifically focusing on lower secondary school principals remains limited. Existing studies on school principals have primarily focused on competency standards, leadership capacity, or general management development, rather than systematically analyzing principals' roles, responsibilities, and competency requirements from a job position perspective. Moreover, there is a lack of research linking job position-based competency frameworks with key processes such as planning, recruitment, training, evaluation, and professional development of principals.

Overall, previous studies have confirmed the critical role of school principals in educational development and highlighted the importance of leadership capacity, professional standards, and human resource development strategies. They have also provided valuable theoretical foundations on job positions and competency frameworks in the public sector. However, significant research gaps remain, particularly in relation to lower secondary school principals. Specifically, there is a lack of comprehensive studies that clearly define the job position of lower secondary school principals as a distinct managerial role, establish a systematic competency framework aligned with this position, and apply it consistently across all stages of personnel development. In addition, no studies have comprehensively examined the development of lower secondary school principals based on a job position approach in the specific context of the North Central region of Vietnam.

Therefore, this study aims to examine the development of lower secondary school principals in the North Central region based on a job position approach, thereby contributing to both theoretical understanding and practical solutions for improving school leadership and educational quality.

2. RESEARCH SUBJECTS AND METHODS

2.1. Research Subjects and Scope

The research focuses on lower secondary school principals in the context of general education reform. The main subject of the study is the development of this group based on a job position approach.

The study aims to: (i) establish the theoretical foundation for developing principals based on job positions; (ii) assess the current situation in the North Central region of Vietnam; and (iii) propose and validate feasible solutions, including piloting one selected intervention.

The research is limited to the development of lower secondary school principals in alignment with the national standards for school principals (MOET, 2018). Empirical data were collected from three provinces in the North Central region (Thanh Hoa, Nghe An, and Ha Tinh) during the 2024–2025 academic years.

2.2. Research Approaches

This study adopts a combination of complementary approaches:

- System approach: The development of school principals is examined as an integrated system, including structure, quantity, quality, and influencing factors. Solutions are designed to ensure coherence across all stages such as planning, recruitment, training, evaluation, and policy implementation.

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- Job position approach (core approach): This approach emphasizes defining job roles, responsibilities, and competency requirements as a basis for personnel development. It serves as the central framework guiding all human resource management activities.
 - Standards-based approach: The study is aligned with the professional standards for school principals, which serve as benchmarks for assessment and development.
 - Human resource development approach: Principals are viewed as key human capital, and their development involves comprehensive strategies, including planning, training, motivation, and creating supportive working environments.
 - Practical approach: The research is grounded in the socio-economic and educational context of the North Central region, ensuring that proposed solutions are contextually relevant and feasible.
- Among these, the job position approach serves as the dominant theoretical perspective of the study.

2.3. Research Methods

This study adopts a comprehensive and integrated research design combining multiple theoretical approaches and methodological tools to investigate the development of lower secondary school principals in the North Central region of Vietnam based on a job position approach. Firstly, a systems approach is employed to examine the development of school principals as a holistic process involving interrelated elements such as quantity, structure, quality, and contextual influencing factors. This approach ensures that proposed solutions address all stages of human resource development, including planning, recruitment, appointment, training, evaluation, and policy implementation. Secondly, the job position approach, which serves as the core perspective of the study, focuses on defining job roles, responsibilities, and competency requirements as the foundation for managing and developing educational personnel. This approach emphasizes aligning all human resource activities with clearly defined competency frameworks associated with specific job positions. In addition, a standards-based approach is applied by using the professional standards for school principals issued by the Ministry of Education and Training as benchmarks for evaluation and development. The human resource development approach is also utilized to consider principals as key human capital, highlighting the importance of systematic strategies for capacity building, motivation, and the creation of supportive working environments. Furthermore, a practical approach is adopted to ensure that the research and proposed solutions are grounded in the socio-economic, cultural, and educational realities of the North Central region.

In terms of methodology, the study employs a combination of theoretical and empirical methods. Theoretical methods include document analysis and synthesis of policies, legal documents, and previous studies related to educational leadership and job position-based management, as well as generalization techniques to systematize theoretical perspectives and clarify key concepts. Empirical data are collected through questionnaire surveys administered to educational managers, principals, vice-principals, and teachers; in-depth interviews with experts and educational leaders; and expert consultations to assess the necessity and feasibility of proposed solutions. In addition, document analysis is conducted on school plans, reports, and management records to supplement primary data. A pilot experiment is also implemented to test one selected solution in practice and evaluate its effectiveness. Quantitative data are processed using statistical methods with the support of SPSS 20.0 software, enabling reliable analysis and interpretation of findings. This combination of approaches and methods provides a robust scientific basis for assessing the current situation and proposing feasible solutions for developing lower secondary school principals in the context of ongoing educational reform.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND KEY DEFINITIONS

In the education system, the school principal is recognized as the head of an educational institution, responsible for organizing, managing, and directing all school activities to achieve educational objectives. From a management perspective, the principal performs core managerial functions, including planning, organizing, leading, and evaluating educational processes (Tran Kiem, 2004). At the same time, the principal acts as both a leader and manager who shapes school development, mobilizes resources, and ensures the quality of education (Bui Minh Hien & Nguyen Vu Bich Hien, 2015). From a legal perspective, national regulations define the principal as the individual accountable for the overall operation of the school, including the implementation of educational plans, management of staff and students, and responsibility for educational outcomes (MOET, 2020). Based on these perspectives, a lower secondary school principal can be understood as the head of a lower secondary institution who is responsible for leading, managing, and organizing all educational activities in accordance with national regulations and educational objectives.

The concept of a “team of principals” refers not merely to a collection of individuals holding leadership positions but to an organized managerial force that plays a critical role in the functioning and development of the education system. In general terms, a team is defined as a group of individuals sharing common professional roles and organized to accomplish shared goals (Vietnamese Dictionary Institute, 2003). In the field of education, educational managers, including principals, constitute a core

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force responsible for organizing and operating educational activities and ensuring system effectiveness (Nguyen Thi My Loc, 2012). Previous studies have emphasized that the effectiveness of school management and educational quality largely depends on the capacity and performance of this group (Pham Ngoc Hai, 2012). Accordingly, the team of lower secondary school principals can be defined as a group of individuals holding principal positions within a specific administrative scope, responsible for leading and managing school activities to achieve educational goals.

In modern human resource management, the concept of job position has become a central element, particularly in public sector reform. According to Government regulations, a job position is defined as a job associated with a specific title, function, and organizational structure, determined based on tasks and responsibilities within an organization (Government of Vietnam, 2012, 2020). From a research perspective, job positions are understood as the basis for identifying job requirements, responsibilities, and competency standards for individuals (Trinh Xuan Thang, 2016). Scholars have also highlighted the importance of job analysis in defining job positions and establishing competency requirements, which serve as the foundation for recruitment, evaluation, and professional development (Bui Thi Phuong Thao, 2016). Therefore, a job position encompasses not only a formal title but also a set of responsibilities, authority, and competency requirements. Based on this understanding, the job position approach refers to a method of human resource management and development that is grounded in the specific requirements of each job position, ensuring that all activities such as recruitment, utilization, training, and evaluation are aligned with clearly defined competency frameworks.

Within the context of human resource development, developing a team of principals involves systematic and purposeful actions aimed at improving their quantity, structure, and quality to meet organizational goals (Phan Van Kha, 2006). In the education sector, this process includes planning, recruitment, appointment, training, professional development, utilization, and evaluation of educational managers to enhance their capacity and effectiveness (Pham Ngoc Hai, 2012). When applying the job position approach, the development of principals must be based on clearly defined roles, responsibilities, and competency requirements associated with their positions. Accordingly, the development of lower secondary school principals based on a job position approach can be understood as a systematic and planned process undertaken by educational authorities to build and enhance the principal workforce in terms of quantity, structure, and quality. This process is grounded in the identification of job positions, functions, responsibilities, and competency frameworks, and it involves coordinated activities such as planning, recruitment, appointment, utilization, training, and evaluation to meet the demands of school governance and educational reform. This concept serves as the central analytical framework of the study, guiding both the theoretical analysis and the empirical investigation of principal development in the North Central region of Vietnam.

4. COMPETENCY FRAMEWORK FOR LOWER SECONDARY SCHOOL PRINCIPALS BASED ON A JOB POSITION APPROACH

In modern human resource management, competency frameworks serve as essential tools for identifying the knowledge, skills, and attributes required to perform effectively in a specific job position (Nguyen Tien Hung, 2017). In the public sector, competency frameworks linked to job positions provide a scientific basis for recruitment, utilization, training, and evaluation of personnel. In the field of general education, the professional standards for school principals issued by the Ministry of Education and Training establish fundamental requirements for leadership and school governance competencies in the context of educational reform (MOET, 2018).

Building on legal regulations and previous research on educational leadership, this study proposes a competency framework for lower secondary school principals based on a job position approach. The framework is structured to reflect core requirements of school leadership and management in the current reform context, encompassing key domains of competencies rather than fragmented tasks or roles.

Specifically, the framework includes six major competency domains. First, leadership and school governance competencies represent the core capacity of principals, including strategic vision development, school planning, organization, leadership, quality assurance, and overall school management. Second, educational management competencies focus on organizing and directing teaching and learning activities, implementing the curriculum, innovating teaching methods, assessing student outcomes, and coordinating with families and communities. Third, teacher development competencies emphasize workforce planning, recruitment, utilization, professional development, performance evaluation, and motivation of teachers, ensuring the sustainability and quality of the teaching staff.

Fourth, resource management competencies involve the effective planning, mobilization, allocation, and utilization of financial, physical, and social resources, along with ensuring transparency and accountability. Fifth, competencies in building an educational environment relate to establishing a democratic, safe, and supportive school culture, fostering positive learning conditions, and strengthening collaboration between schools, families, and communities. Finally, information technology and

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innovation competencies highlight the ability to apply digital tools in school management, utilize data for decision-making, promote digital transformation, and drive innovation in school governance.

Overall, this competency framework reflects an integrated and systematic approach to principal development, aligning job position requirements with competency-based management. It serves as a central analytical tool for assessing current capacities and guiding the development of lower secondary school principals in response to ongoing educational reform and increasing demands for modern school governance.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Perceptions of the Importance of Developing Lower Secondary School Principals under a Job-Position Approach

In the context of fundamental and comprehensive educational reform, lower secondary school principals play a pivotal role in school management and development. From a modern human resource management perspective, developing school leaders should follow a job-position approach, aligning individual competencies with the specific requirements of each position.

Table 1. Awareness of the Importance of Developing Lower Secondary School Principals Based on a Job-Position Approach

Survey content	Thanh Hoa		Nghe An		Ha Tinh		F	Sig.
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Developing principals based on a job-position approach is an essential requirement of educational management reform	4.45	0.52	4.38	0.55	4.21	0.63	4.72	0.01*
Developing principals based on a job-position approach contributes to improving school governance effectiveness	4.41	0.54	4.34	0.58	4.18	0.65	3.98	0.02*
Developing principals based on a job-position approach contributes to improving school educational quality	4.39	0.56	4.31	0.60	4.20	0.64	2.87	0.06
Clearly defining the competency framework of principals improves recruitment and appointment effectiveness	4.36	0.58	4.28	0.61	4.10	0.69	4.15	0.02*
Developing principals based on a job-position approach improves the effectiveness of training and professional development for school managers	4.38	0.55	4.30	0.59	4.16	0.66	3.21	0.04*
A job-position approach enhances transparency and objectivity in principal evaluation	4.30	0.60	4.24	0.63	4.05	0.71	4.36	0.01*

A survey of 310 respondents—including leaders of Departments of Education and Training and lower secondary school principals in Thanh Hóa, Nghệ An, and Hà Tĩnh—was conducted to assess perceptions of this approach. Results show a high level of agreement on its importance, with an overall mean score of 4.29/5.00, indicating strong awareness among educational managers.

The statement “developing principals based on job positions is an inevitable requirement of educational management reform” received the highest rating (Mean = 4.35), with statistically significant differences among provinces ($p = 0.01$), particularly higher in Thanh Hóa. Similarly, the role of principal development in improving school governance was highly rated (Mean = 4.31), also showing significant regional differences ($p = 0.02$).

The criterion related to establishing competency frameworks for principal recruitment and appointment was rated positively (Mean = 4.25), reflecting growing recognition of competency-based management. In contrast, perceptions of its impact on improving school education quality showed no significant regional differences ($p = 0.06$), suggesting a relatively consistent view across provinces.

Notably, perceptions of the role of the job-position approach in enhancing transparency and objectivity in principal evaluation varied significantly among provinces ($p = 0.01$), indicating uneven understanding of its application in practice.

These findings indicate that stakeholders generally hold strong awareness of the importance of developing principals under a job-position approach. However, differences across provinces suggest uneven adoption of modern HR management perspectives. While awareness is relatively high, further efforts are needed to translate this understanding into effective implementation in practice.

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5.2. Planning for the Development of Lower Secondary School Principals under a Job-Position Approach

Planning the development of school principals is a key component of educational human resource development. Under the job-position approach, such planning should be based on forecasting leadership needs, defining competency requirements for the principal position, and identifying appropriate personnel sources. Effective planning not only ensures continuity and stability in school leadership but also provides a foundation for training, development, and future appointments.

A survey examining needs assessment, planning processes, personnel selection, and workforce forecasting shows that this activity in the North Central region is rated at a moderately good level (Mean = 3.76/5.00). This indicates that while planning has been implemented, certain limitations remain.

Specifically, identifying leadership needs aligned with job-position requirements achieved a mean of 3.79, with significant differences across provinces ($p = 0.01$), where Thanh Hóa performed better than Nghệ An and Hà Tĩnh. Similarly, aligning planning with local educational development strategies was rated at 3.78, also showing significant variation ($p = 0.03$), suggesting uneven implementation.

The selection of potential leaders from teaching and management staff was relatively well performed (Mean = 3.83), with no significant differences among provinces ($p = 0.09$), indicating a similar approach across the region.

Notably, aligning planning with competency frameworks for the principal position received the lowest rating (Mean = 3.70) and showed strong statistical differences ($p = 0.00$). This suggests that although the concept of job-position management has been introduced, its practical application—particularly the use of competency frameworks in planning—remains inconsistent.

These findings indicate that principal workforce planning has been initiated and contributes to leadership continuity; however, its alignment with job-position requirements is still limited. Variations across provinces further reflect differences in local management capacity and human resource policies. Strengthening competency-based planning is therefore essential to improve the quality of school leadership development.

Table 2. Current Status of Planning and Developing Lower Secondary School Principals Based on a Job-Position Approach

Survey content	Thanh Hoa		Nghe An		Ha Tinh		F	Sig.
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Identifying the development needs of principals aligned with job-position requirements	3.92	0.61	3.81	0.65	3.65	0.71	5.12	0.01*
Developing planning strategies for principals in accordance with local educational development orientations	3.88	0.63	3.79	0.66	3.68	0.70	3.45	0.03*
Selecting potential management personnel from teachers and school staff	3.90	0.62	3.84	0.64	3.75	0.69	2.41	0.09
Forecasting the demand for principal development in different stages	3.85	0.65	3.76	0.67	3.61	0.73	4.28	0.02*
Aligning principal planning with the competency framework of the job position	3.83	0.66	3.72	0.69	3.55	0.74	6.03	0.00*

5.3. Selection, Appointment, Utilization, and Mobility of Lower Secondary School Principals under a Job-Position Approach

The selection, appointment, dismissal, utilization, and rotation of school principals are critical components of educational leadership development. Under the job-position approach, these processes should be grounded in clearly defined competency requirements, ensuring alignment between individual capabilities and job demands.

A survey conducted in the North Central region indicates that these practices are implemented at a moderately good level (Mean = 3.74/5.00). While personnel management has been relatively well established, its alignment with job-position requirements remains limited.

Selecting principals based on competency standards achieved a mean of 3.75, with significant differences among provinces ($p = 0.01$), suggesting uneven application of competency-based criteria. The transparency of appointment processes was rated relatively high (Mean = 3.82), also showing significant variation ($p = 0.04$), indicating differences in implementation across localities.

The use of principals in positions matching their qualifications and experience reached a mean of 3.77, with no significant regional differences ($p = 0.05$), reflecting generally consistent practices. Rotation of principals to enhance leadership capacity scored 3.69 and showed significant differences ($p = 0.03$), suggesting that this measure has been applied selectively to support leadership development.

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In contrast, the removal or replacement of underperforming principals received the lowest rating (Mean = 3.63) and showed no significant differences ($p = 0.11$), indicating ongoing challenges in performance-based management.

These findings suggest that while core personnel processes are in place, the integration of competency-based approaches remains incomplete. Greater emphasis is needed on aligning leadership selection and utilization with job-position requirements, as well as strengthening accountability mechanisms to ensure effective school governance in the context of educational reform.

Table 3. Current Status of Recruitment, Appointment, Utilization, and Rotation of Lower Secondary School Principals Based on a Job-Position Approach

Survey content	Thanh Hoa		Nghe An		Ha Tinh		F	Sig.
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Recruitment of principals based on competency standards of the job position	3.88	0.63	3.76	0.66	3.60	0.72	4.98	0.01*
The appointment process is conducted in a transparent and open manner	3.91	0.60	3.84	0.63	3.70	0.68	3.27	0.04*
Utilization of principals is aligned with their managerial competence and experience	3.86	0.62	3.79	0.65	3.66	0.71	2.94	0.05
Implementation of principal rotation to enhance managerial effectiveness	3.80	0.66	3.70	0.69	3.58	0.73	3.64	0.03*
Dismissal or replacement of principals when they fail to meet job requirements	3.72	0.68	3.65	0.71	3.52	0.75	2.21	0.11
Alignment between principals' competencies and school development requirements	3.85	0.64	3.77	0.67	3.61	0.72	4.12	0.02*

5.4. Professional Development of Lower Secondary School Principals under a Job-Position Approach

In educational human resource management, professional development is a key component of leadership development. Under the job-position approach, training for principals should be designed based on competency requirements, ensuring alignment with individual needs and career stages.

A survey in the North Central region indicates that professional development activities are implemented at a moderately good level (Mean = 3.77/5.00). However, the linkage between training content and job-position competency requirements remains limited.

Identifying training needs based on competency requirements scored 3.73, with significant differences across provinces ($p = 0.01$), suggesting that needs assessment is not yet systematic. Similarly, planning training programs aligned with competency frameworks received a relatively low mean (3.69) and showed significant variation ($p = 0.02$), indicating weak integration with competency-based approaches.

The relevance of training content to school management competencies was rated higher (Mean = 3.81), with significant differences ($p = 0.04$), reflecting uneven quality across localities. Meanwhile, the organization of diverse training formats was relatively well rated (Mean = 3.86), with no significant differences ($p = 0.10$), suggesting similar implementation methods, mainly through workshops and formal training programs.

Evaluation of training effectiveness received one of the lowest scores (Mean = 3.69) and showed significant differences ($p = 0.01$), indicating that assessment practices are inconsistent and not yet fully developed.

These findings suggest that while professional development for principals is regularly implemented and contributes to improving management capacity, it still relies largely on traditional approaches. Stronger alignment with competency frameworks and more systematic evaluation mechanisms are needed to enhance the effectiveness of training under a job-position approach.

Table 4. Current Status of Professional Development for Lower Secondary School Principals Based on a Job-Position Approach

Survey content	Thanh Hoa		Nghe An		Ha Tinh		F	Sig.
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Identifying principals' training needs based on	3.85	0.64	3.74	0.68	3.60	0.72	4.76	0.01*

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job-position competency requirements								
Developing training plans aligned with the school management competency framework	3.81	0.66	3.70	0.69	3.56	0.74	4.11	0.02*
Training content meets the requirements for developing school governance competencies	3.89	0.62	3.82	0.65	3.71	0.70	3.18	0.04*
Implementation of diverse training methods (workshops, seminars, experiential learning, etc.)	3.92	0.60	3.86	0.63	3.79	0.67	2.27	0.10
Encouraging principals' self-learning and self-development of managerial competencies	3.95	0.58	3.88	0.61	3.80	0.66	3.01	0.05
Evaluation of the effectiveness of principal training programs	3.80	0.67	3.72	0.70	3.55	0.75	5.24	0.01*

5.5. Current Status of Evaluating Lower Secondary School Principals under the Job-Position Approach

Evaluation of principals is a key component of developing educational leadership. Under the job-position approach, evaluation should align individual performance with job requirements, providing a basis for planning, training, and personnel decisions. In the context of ongoing educational reform, principal evaluation must extend beyond administrative outcomes to include leadership capacity, school governance, staff development, and innovation. Although national standards for principals exist, their application in practice remains inconsistent and sometimes superficial.

Survey results indicate that principal evaluation in the North Central region is implemented at a moderately good level (Mean = 3.76/5.00). This suggests that evaluation practices are in place, but their alignment with job-position requirements is not yet fully realized.

Evaluation based on principal standards and job requirements received a mean score of 3.79, with statistically significant differences across provinces ($p = 0.01$), indicating uneven application. The criterion assessing whether evaluation indicators adequately reflect school governance capacity scored 3.73, also with significant differences ($p = 0.01$), suggesting variations in how evaluation criteria are operationalized locally.

The transparency of evaluation procedures was rated relatively higher (Mean = 3.81), reflecting efforts to ensure openness; however, differences among provinces remain significant ($p = 0.04$). Meanwhile, the use of evaluation results for personnel planning and development was rated lower (Mean = 3.70), indicating limited integration of evaluation outcomes into human resource management.

Similarly, using evaluation results to inform training and professional development scored 3.68, highlighting a weak linkage between evaluation and capacity-building activities.

These findings suggest that while principal evaluation has been widely implemented, several limitations persist. The use of professional standards has improved objectivity, but the connection between evaluation results and workforce development remains insufficient. Strengthening this linkage is essential to ensure that evaluation not only measures performance but also effectively supports the continuous development of school leadership under the job-position approach.

Table 5. Current Status of Evaluation of Lower Secondary School Principals Based on a Job-Position Approach

Survey content	Thanh Hoa		Nghe An		Ha Tinh		F	Sig.
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Evaluation of principals is based on principal standards and job-position requirements	3.92	0.60	3.80	0.65	3.66	0.71	5.42	0.01*
Evaluation criteria fully reflect principals' school governance competencies	3.85	0.63	3.74	0.67	3.59	0.72	4.63	0.01*
The evaluation process is conducted in a transparent and open manner	3.90	0.61	3.82	0.64	3.70	0.69	3.11	0.04*
Evaluation results are used in planning and developing the principal workforce	3.84	0.64	3.72	0.68	3.55	0.73	4.27	0.02*
Evaluation results are used as a basis for training and professional development	3.81	0.65	3.70	0.69	3.52	0.75	3.89	0.02*
Principal evaluation accurately reflects managerial competence and school performance	3.86	0.63	3.75	0.67	3.60	0.72	3.45	0.03*

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5.6. Current Status of Conditions Ensuring the Development of Lower Secondary School Principals under the Job-Position Approach

Ensuring appropriate conditions—such as governance mechanisms, personnel policies, financial resources, and supportive organizational environments—is essential for developing principals under the job-position approach. These conditions enable effective planning, recruitment, training, and evaluation, while also motivating principals to enhance their leadership and management capacities.

Survey results show that these enabling conditions in the North Central region are at a moderately good level (Mean = 3.77/5.00). This indicates that localities have begun to establish necessary foundations for leadership development, although notable limitations remain.

The availability of comprehensive and consistent policy frameworks for principal management received the highest rating (Mean = 3.84), with significant differences across provinces ($p = 0.01$), suggesting uneven policy implementation. The clarity of management and decentralization mechanisms was rated at 3.77 ($p = 0.02$), indicating that while governance structures are generally defined, their effectiveness varies by locality.

Financial support for training and professional development scored lower (Mean = 3.69), reflecting constraints in funding for leadership development; differences across provinces are also significant ($p = 0.02$), likely linked to varying socio-economic conditions. The working environment supporting principals' leadership capacity was rated relatively higher (Mean = 3.83, $p = 0.04$), suggesting that schools have partially created conditions conducive to effective leadership, though disparities persist.

Coordination among educational authorities in developing principals was rated at 3.73 and did not show statistically significant differences ($p = 0.08$), indicating generally similar but still limited levels of inter-agency collaboration.

These findings suggest that while foundational conditions for principal development have been established, improvements are still needed. In particular, strengthening financial support, refining policy mechanisms, and enhancing coordination among educational authorities are critical to creating a more enabling environment for developing school leaders in line with the job-position approach.

Table 6. Current Status of Conditions Ensuring the Development of Lower Secondary School Principals Based on a Job-Position Approach

Survey content	Thanh Hoa		Nghe An		Ha Tinh		F	Sig.
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Policies and regulatory documents for principal workforce management are sufficiently and consistently issued	3.95	0.59	3.86	0.63	3.70	0.68	4.62	0.01*
Management mechanisms and decentralization of principal governance are clear and supportive of workforce development	3.88	0.62	3.79	0.66	3.65	0.71	3.74	0.02*
Funding for principal training and professional development is adequately ensured	3.80	0.65	3.71	0.69	3.55	0.74	4.15	0.02*
The working environment enables principals to effectively demonstrate leadership and management competencies	3.92	0.60	3.84	0.63	3.72	0.68	3.27	0.04*
Incentive and motivation mechanisms for principal competency development are in place	3.85	0.64	3.76	0.67	3.60	0.72	3.11	0.04*

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Coordination among educational management agencies in developing the principal workforce	3.83	0.65	3.75	0.69	3.61	0.73	2.54	0.08
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6. PROPOSED SOLUTIONS FOR DEVELOPING THE TEAM OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS USING A JOB-BASED APPROACH

6.1. Developing a Planning Framework for Lower Secondary School Principals Aligned with Local Educational Development

This solution aims to establish a strategic and forward-looking planning system for lower secondary school principals in the North Central region, ensuring a qualified pool of school leaders who meet job-position requirements in the context of educational reform.

The core content focuses on identifying, selecting, and developing potential candidates with appropriate professional qualities, leadership capacity, and growth potential. Planning should be grounded in local education development strategies, school network demands, and a competency framework for principals, ensuring alignment between individual capabilities and job requirements. The planning process should be open and dynamic, allowing for regular review, adjustment, and inclusion of new qualified candidates.

Implementation involves four key steps: (1) defining planning objectives and standards based on national regulations and competency frameworks; (2) assessing the current pool of principals and potential candidates; (3) developing phased planning aligned with local education needs; and (4) regularly reviewing and updating the plan to ensure relevance and flexibility.

Effective implementation requires strong awareness among educational authorities, close coordination between management levels, adequate resource allocation, and opportunities for planned candidates to participate in training and professional development programs.

This solution contributes to ensuring a sufficient, well-structured, and high-quality principal workforce, while also supporting career orientation and capacity development for future school leaders.

6.2. Selection and Utilization of Lower Secondary School Principals Based on Job-Position Requirements

This solution aims to ensure that the selection, appointment, and utilization of lower secondary school principals are aligned with clearly defined job-position requirements. It seeks to identify and appoint individuals with appropriate professional qualities and strong leadership and management capacities, thereby improving school governance and supporting educational reform.

The core approach is to base selection on a competency framework for principals, including leadership, school governance, instructional management, staff development, resource management, and ICT application. Recruitment processes should be transparent, competitive, and merit-based, moving beyond traditional criteria such as seniority.

Implementation involves four main steps: (1) defining clear standards and competency requirements for the principal position; (2) organizing transparent and competitive selection procedures (e.g., application review, competency assessment, interviews, or development proposals); (3) assigning and utilizing principals flexibly according to their strengths, including rotation or reassignment when appropriate; and (4) strengthening monitoring and performance evaluation to inform personnel decisions and professional development.

Effective implementation requires well-developed competency standards, enhanced human resource management capacity at the local level, strong coordination among educational authorities, and appropriate incentive policies to motivate principals.

This solution contributes to improving the quality and effectiveness of school leadership by ensuring a strong alignment between individual competencies and job requirements.

6.3. Organizing professional development for lower secondary school principals

This solution aims to enhance the leadership and management capacity of lower secondary school principals in the North Central region of Vietnam in line with job-position requirements, in the context of general education reform, digital transformation, and increased school autonomy. It focuses on updating principals' knowledge of school governance, developing key competencies such as resource management, teacher development, ICT application, digital transformation, and change leadership, and improving their ability to apply these competencies in practical school management. The solution also emphasizes strengthening both existing and newly required competencies to meet evolving educational demands and to improve school performance.

The content of the professional development program is based on a competency-based job-position framework and the current competency requirements and practical challenges of lower secondary school principals. It includes six main components: awareness of the job-position approach; leadership and school governance competencies (vision building, strategic planning,

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change management, and quality assurance); educational management competencies (curriculum implementation, teaching and assessment management, and experiential education); teacher development competencies (needs analysis, staff assignment, in-service training, and professional learning communities); resource management competencies (financial management, facilities, social mobilization, and school culture); and digital transformation competencies (data use, digital systems, online administration, and communication platforms).

Implementation begins with clearly defining objectives, focusing on developing principals' competencies according to job-position requirements while addressing both competency gaps and areas needing improvement. Training activities are designed to be needs-based, competency-oriented, practice-focused, and supportive of long-term professional development and innovation in school governance.

Next, a structured training plan is developed based on competency gaps, local needs, and available resources. The plan clearly specifies objectives, content, methods, participants, timeline, human resources, budget, and evaluation criteria, ensuring feasibility and alignment with practice through the SMART principle.

The training program is designed in a modular, competency-based structure, including modules on leadership and governance, educational management, teacher development, resource management, school environment development, and digital transformation. Each module defines objectives, learning outcomes, activities, outputs, and assessment methods, with strong emphasis on practical application, case studies, and problem-solving tasks.

The implementation process follows five steps: analyzing current competency levels of principals, identifying training needs, developing training plans and programs, organizing implementation, and evaluating outcomes. Evaluation focuses on participation, achievement of learning outcomes, and the ability to apply knowledge and skills in real school management practice.

Various forms of professional development are flexibly combined, including face-to-face training, online learning, blended learning, cluster-based professional learning communities, guided self-study, and case-based training. This combination ensures flexibility, accessibility, and effectiveness, especially in the context of digital transformation in education.

Finally, effective implementation requires strong commitment from educational management authorities, a clear competency framework, qualified trainers and experts, adequate time and resources, and a robust monitoring and post-training support mechanism to ensure that acquired competencies are effectively transferred into school management practice.

6.4. Building a supportive environment and enabling conditions for lower secondary school principals to develop leadership and school management competencies

The solution aims to establish a favorable management environment and necessary enabling conditions for lower secondary school principals in the North Central region of Vietnam to fully develop and effectively exercise their leadership and school management competencies in accordance with job-position requirements. In practice, a principal's competence is not determined solely by individual qualifications and skills but is also strongly influenced by the working environment, management mechanisms, and available institutional conditions. Therefore, creating a supportive governance environment and appropriate enabling conditions is essential for enhancing principals' performance, improving school effectiveness, and promoting the sustainable development of lower secondary education.

The content of the solution focuses on several key aspects. First, it emphasizes building a democratic, transparent, and innovation-friendly educational governance environment that encourages school-based initiatives. In such an environment, principals are empowered to proactively develop school plans, organize educational activities, and implement innovations to improve educational quality. Second, it highlights the need to strengthen coordination mechanisms among educational management agencies and schools, particularly between Departments of Education and Training, Divisions of Education and Training, and schools, in order to provide coherent support for school governance. Third, it requires ensuring adequate conditions in terms of infrastructure, financial resources, and educational inputs so that principals can effectively carry out their managerial responsibilities. Finally, it promotes the development of a professional learning and exchange environment among principals through experience sharing, professional dialogue, and inter-school collaboration, thereby supporting continuous professional growth and adaptation to educational change.

The implementation of the solution requires several key actions. First, it is necessary to improve governance mechanisms and decentralization in education management, thereby granting greater autonomy to schools and enabling principals to exercise proactive leadership and decision-making. Second, local authorities should strengthen investment in school infrastructure, teaching equipment, and digital infrastructure, while ensuring efficient use of educational resources to support school operations. Third, professional learning networks should be established, including forums, workshops, and communities of practice for principals, to facilitate experience sharing and collective learning. Fourth, appropriate incentive and motivation policies should be

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implemented to encourage principals' continuous professional development and enhance their commitment to school improvement.

Finally, the effective implementation of this solution requires several essential conditions. These include strong leadership and policy support from educational authorities in creating a favorable governance environment; adequate financial and material resources for school development; effective coordination mechanisms among education authorities, schools, and relevant stakeholders; and opportunities for principals to participate in professional learning activities, experience sharing, and leadership development programs to continuously improve their management capacity.

7. EXPERIMENTAL IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED SOLUTION

7.1. Purpose of the Experiment

The experiment was conducted to verify the effectiveness of the proposed solution: "Developing training programs to enhance the managerial competence of lower secondary school principals based on job-position approach."

The intervention aimed to assess changes in principals' school management competencies after participating in a training program designed in line with innovation and digital transformation in educational management, consistent with the spirit of Resolution No. 57-NQ/TW and Resolution No. 71-NQ/TW of the Politburo.

7.2. Experimental Content

The training program was designed as competency-based modules focusing on school management in the context of digital transformation, including:

- Leadership for change in schools;
- Management of educational activities in digital environments;
- Application of ICT and data in school management;
- Development of teaching staff in educational innovation;
- Building an innovative school culture.

These contents align with Resolution 57-NQ/TW, emphasizing science, technology, innovation, and digital transformation as key drivers of development.

The experiment involved 30 lower secondary school principals in Nghe An province. Participants were selected through convenience sampling, ensuring relatively representative coverage across localities.

7.3. Experimental Design and Procedure

The study employed a pre-test and post-test design to assess changes in competency levels before and after the intervention.

The experiment began with the design of the training program, which was structured into competency-based modules. Participants were then selected based on their training needs and willingness to participate.

The training implementation included assigning learning tasks, providing learning materials, organizing group discussions, facilitating expert feedback, and guiding participants in refining their managerial outputs based on real school contexts. This process ensured active engagement and practical application of knowledge.

The evaluation phase was conducted after the training using a combination of self-assessment, expert assessment, and analysis of participants' management products. Quantitative comparisons between pre-test and post-test results were used to determine the effectiveness of the intervention.

7.4. Experimental Instruments

A standardized set of evaluation instruments was used to ensure objectivity and reliability. Competency levels were measured using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from very low to very high.

The competency framework covered five domains: leadership and school management, educational activity management, teacher development, resource management, and ICT and digital transformation. Each domain included specific behavioral indicators reflecting principals' professional competencies.

Table 7. Competency Assessment Framework

Competency Group	Evaluation Criteria
Leadership and school management	Vision building; strategic planning; implementation; decision-making
Educational activity management	Curriculum implementation; teaching management; assessment; holistic education
Teacher development	Assignment; professional development; motivation;

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	evaluation
Resource management	Financial management; facilities; resource mobilization; efficiency
ICT & digital transformation	Software use; data utilization; digital management; digital working environment

7.5. Experimental Results

Data were analyzed using SPSS 20.0, including descriptive statistics, paired sample t-test, Cronbach's Alpha, and Cohen's d effect size.

(1) Pre-test and Post-test Comparison

Table 8. Changes in principals' competencies before and after intervention

Competency Group	Pre Mean	Post Mean	Difference
Leadership & school management	3.42	3.96	+0.54
Educational activity management	3.47	3.88	+0.41
Teacher development	3.35	3.79	+0.44
Resource management	3.31	3.36	+0.45
ICT & digital transformation	3.18	3.92	+0.74

Overall, all competency groups improved, with the strongest increase in ICT and digital transformation, followed by leadership and school management.

(2) Paired Sample T-test Results

Table 9. Paired Sample T-test

Competency Group	Pre Mean	Post Mean	t	p-value
Leadership & school management	3.42	3.96	5.21	0.000
Educational activity management	3.47	3.88	3.94	0.001
Teacher development	3.35	3.79	4.12	0.000
Resource management	3.31	3.36	0.82	0.417
ICT & digital transformation	3.18	3.92	6.48	0.000

The results show statistically significant improvements in most competency areas ($p < 0.01$), except resource management ($p > 0.05$). The strongest effect was observed in ICT and digital transformation.

(3) Reliability of Measurement Scale

The Cronbach's Alpha values ranged from 0.82 to 0.90, indicating high internal consistency of all measurement scales.

Table 10. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability

Competency Group	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Leadership & school management	6	0.89
Educational activity management	5	0.86
Teacher development	5	0.87
Resource management	4	0.82
ICT & digital transformation	4	0.90

(4) Effect Size (Cohen's d)

Effect size analysis shows that the intervention had strong to very strong effects on most competencies, particularly ICT and digital transformation.

Table 11. Effect Size of the Intervention

Competency Group	Cohen's d	Impact level
Leadership & school management	0.82	Large
Educational activity management	0.61	Medium
Teacher development	0.65	Medium
Resource management	0.09	Very small
ICT & digital transformation	1.02	Very large

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The experimental results confirm that the proposed job-position-based training solution has a positive and statistically significant impact on the development of lower secondary school principals' competencies.

The strongest improvements were observed in competencies related to leadership, innovation, and digital transformation. However, resource management showed minimal change, indicating that this competency requires longer-term development strategies and broader institutional support beyond short-term training interventions.

Overall, the findings provide empirical evidence supporting the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed solution for developing lower secondary school principals in the North Central region of Vietnam.

8. CONCLUSION

This study emphasizes the critical role of lower secondary school principals in school leadership and quality improvement within the context of comprehensive education reform in Vietnam. Developing principals based on a job-position approach is identified as an essential requirement to enhance school governance effectiveness.

The research clarified key theoretical issues on principal development, including concepts, competency requirements, and core development components such as planning, recruitment, training, evaluation, and professional environment. Empirical findings show that while principals generally meet basic requirements, limitations remain in governance capacity, innovation, and adaptation to curriculum reform, and current management practices are not fully aligned with job-position requirements.

Based on these findings, the study proposes a coherent system of solutions covering competency-based planning, recruitment, professional development, performance evaluation, and enabling working environments. Survey results confirm that these solutions are highly feasible and necessary.

Overall, the study provides both theoretical and practical contributions to improving the quality of lower secondary school principals and enhancing school governance effectiveness in the context of educational reform.

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